

Education

July 2024

The Western Balkans Agenda on Innovation, Research, Education, Culture, Youth and Sport is a long-term strategy from the EU and the Western Balkans (WB) for cooperation with the region. It will contribute to the region's economic and societal development and builds on three main pillars: Political, Thematic, and Regional.

The implementation of the Western Balkans Agenda is monitored by the project POLICY ANSWERS, and the wider context, progress and achievements are summarised in regular reports. In this brief report card, you find the results of the second round of data collection during 2023 and the first months of 2024 and a comparison with the baseline data collected in the previous round.

In terms of Education, the monitoring focuses on the context indicator "Learning-adjusted schooling years" and on a variety of achievements outlined in the WB Agenda (see next page).

Achievements in a wider context of the Western Balkans Agenda

Note
Data for 2019 not available

Source
World Bank <https://tinyurl.com/sourceindicator> (accessed 29 March 2024).
More information on the indicator: <https://tinyurl.com/moreaboutind>

* This designation is without prejudice to positions on status, and is in line with UNSCR 1244/1999 and the ICJ Opinion on the Kosovo declaration of independence.

Regional Indicator

Western Balkans Steering Platform meetings on Education and Training

Western Balkans Economy Indicators

	Integration & stronger participation in EU programmes and initiatives				Fostered capacity building for R&I, education and VET	
	Supporting the implementation of acquis					
Albania	No projects & missions					
Bosnia and Herzegovina	No projects & missions					
Kosovo*	One bilateral TA project No missions					
Montenegro	No projects & missions					
North Macedonia	No new projects & no missions					
Serbia	No projects & missions					

Legend: Information not available

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Highlights

Successful participation of Western Balkans universities in the European University alliances

POLICY ANSWERS supports the Western Balkans eco-system through dedicated capacity building measures

